

Psychological status among the elderly aged men

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Abstract

Objective: The main purpose of the study is to observe the differences of Anxiety and Stress level among the elderly aged men.

Subjects: Seventy One (N=71) Elderly aged men were randomly selected as subject for the present study from Nadia District of West Bengal, India. The age range from 60 to 75 years.

Group division: All the Subjects were divided into three groups: (i) Elderly aged men (N=25) residing in old age homes, (ii) elderly aged men (N=30) Home dwellers living with family and (iii) elderly aged men (N=16) home dwellers living alone.

Methods: The psychological status components, Anxiety and Stress of elderly aged male were measured through the Spielberger Anxiety Expression Inventory Questionnaire (1970) and the Stress Inventory Questionnaire (2001) adopted by Srivastava.A.K, respectively.

Statistical analysis: to find out the significance differences in psychological status among the groups, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. To locate exact differences within the different groups Tukey's LSD test was adopted as post hoc test. The significance of means were tested at $p < 0.05$ level. For the statistical calculations, excel spread sheet of window version 7 was used.

Result: It was observed that f value was significant at 0.05 levels. Tukey's post hoc test observed significant differences between the groups in State anxiety, Trait Anxiety and Stress (Cognitive Approach)

Key words: State Anxiety, Trait Anxiety, Stress, Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach and Behavioral Avoidance.

1. Introduction

Asia and Europe are residence to some of the world's oldest population of ages 65 and above, were the Japan is at the top with 28% of old population and followed by Italy at 23%. According to Census 2011, India has 104 million older people (60+years) who occupy 8.6% of total population. The population of older people all over the world is prospective to almost double to 19.5% in 2050. This means that every 1 in 5 Indians is likely to be a senior citizen, among them 4.9% of population living alone aged 60 and above (E. Ortiz-Ospina, 2013).

As people grow older, they often have to face many problems like declining health and mobility leading to social isolation and loneliness. Many senior citizens also suffer from insomnia and behavioral disorders, cognitive downfall or confusion, hearing loss, problem of eye, back and neck pain and osteoarthritis, pulmonary disease, diabetes, depression states as a result of physical disorders. Mental health problems are also common among elder and may involve in anxiety disorders, Alzheimer's disease, and craziness (WHO). According to the study of National Council of Aging nearly above 92% of older population has at least one chronic disease and 77% have at least two. Cardiovascular diseases like heart disease, diabetes, stroke and cancer are among the common and expensive chronic health problem responsible for two-thirds of death each year (www.ncoa.org).

The loneliness and social isolation are the most common caused by low-quality social relationships and other causes being age 70 or older, having chronic health disease problems, and changing family structures. While Social contacts favor to decrease as we age due to retirement, death of friends and family, and lack of motility (Cacioppo, 2009).

Migration and family quarrel are the most common causes behind the growing number of old-age homes. Now a day we are mostly involve entire virtual and unfamiliar life, it can be challenging for elders to adjust to their children's new circle. While old age home has limited liberty in the living, the choice of food and lack of privacy. It will not be the same as like in one's own home as well as the atmosphere might not be friendly to the elders (Burton, 2010).

Ageing is a natural aspect with opportunities and challenges. Increase in long life and decrease of joint family concept and breakdown in social fabric pushes seniors into loneliness and neglect. Older people are important resource for any society, hence, healthy life with physical activity, good diet, avoiding tobacco or alcohol and family and social happiness are recommended for physical and mental wellbeing for the senior citizens.

2. Method

3.

Total seventy one (71), elderly aged men of age between 60-75 years were randomly selected from Kalyani, Gayeshpur Municipality and Saguna G.P of Nadia district in West Bengal, India. All the Subjects were divided into three groups: (i) Elderly aged men (N=25) residing in old age homes, (ii) elderly aged men (N=30) Home dwellers living with family and (iii) elderly aged men (N=16) home dwellers living alone. The psychological components, Anxiety (State Anxiety and Trait Anxiety) and

Stress (Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach and Behavioral Avoidance) of elderly aged male were measured through the Spielberger Anxiety Expression Inventory Questionnaire (1970) and the Stress Inventory Questionnaire (2001) adopted by Srivastava.A.K respectively. To find out the significance differences in psychological status among the groups, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. To locate exact differences within the different groups Tukey's LSD test was adopted as post hoc test. The significance of means were tested at $p < 0.05$ level. For the statistical calculations, excel spread sheet of window version 7 was used.

Interpretation of the score: State and Trait Anxiety range from 20 – 80, the higher score indicates the higher level of anxiety and low score indicates the lower level of anxiety. The Stress inventory questionnaire consists of 50 items with five point scale and one can secure a maximum of 4 marks in one question.

Data interpretation: The anxiety and stress level are as follows based on Spielberger's Questionnaire (1970) and Srivastava.A.K's Questionnaire (2001).

State & Trait Anxiety	Stress			
		Low Deficient	Moderate	High Efficient
Below 30 = low anxiety 30 – 40 = slight anxiety 40 – 50 = moderate anxiety Above 50 = over anxiety	Behavioral approach	0 -29	30-45	46-60
	Cognitive approach	0 -11	12-18	19-24
	Behavioral avoidance	0-27	28-48	49-56

3.1. Criterion Measures

The researcher measured the Personal Data and Psychological Variables of the subjects. The measured Personal Data and Psychological Components were as follows-

Table-1: The Personal Data and Psychological Variables measurements

Variables		Measuring Unit	Measured by/ through	
Personal data	Age	Years	DOB	
	Height	Cm	Measuring tape	
	Weight	kg	Weighing machine	
Psychological Variables	Anxiety	State anxiety	Score	Questionnaire
		Trait anxiety		
	Stress	Behavioral Approach	Score	Questionnaire
		Cognitive Approach		
		Behavioral Avoidance		

4. Result and Discussion

The result of the study of selected Psychological Variables and their statistical analysis has been presented in the following heads-

4.1. Personal Data of the Subject:

The mean and SD value of the personal data of three groups were presented in the Table No 2.

Table No. 2. Descriptive statistics of personal data of all the three groups.

Groups	Numbers	Mean \pm SD		
		Age(years)	Height(cm)	Weight(kg)
Residing in old age home	25	64.60 \pm 6.63	150.88 \pm 3.48	60.56 \pm 4.64
Home dwellers living with family	30	65.10 \pm 5.01	152.53 \pm 4.11	58.57 \pm 3.81
Home dwellers living alone	16	67.88 \pm 5.16	152.63 \pm 4.88	61.50 \pm 4.84

Table No- 2, indicates that the mean and SD value of age of elderly aged men residing in old age home , Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone were 64.60 \pm 6.63 years, 65.10 \pm 5.01years and 67.88 \pm 5.16 years respectively. The mean and value SD value of height of Elderly aged males of Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 150.88 \pm 3.48 cm, 152.53 \pm 4.11cm and 152.63 \pm 4.88 cm respectively. Mean and SD value of weight of Elderly aged males of Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 60.56 \pm 4.64 kg, 58.57 \pm 3.81kg and 61.50 \pm 4.84 kg respectively.

Fig 1: Graphical representations of Mean Value of Personal Data of the Subjects

4.2. Psychological Variables (State Anxiety) among the three groups were presented below-

Table No. 3. Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of State Anxiety among Residing in old age homes, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone.

Variables	Group	N	Mean \pm SD	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Ratio
State anxiety	Residing in old age home	25	44.56 \pm 5.00	Between	309.30	2	154.65	4.77*s
	Home dwellers living with family	30	46.37 \pm 6.01	Within	2107.93	65	32.43	
	Home dwellers Living alone	16	50.19 \pm 5.80	Total	2417.24	67		

*The table values required for significance at $F_{0.05}$ level with DF (2, 65) was 3.13

Table no- 3, indicates that the mean value in respect of State Anxiety of the three groups- Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 44.56, 46.37 and 50.19 respectively with SD value were 5.00,6.01 and 5.80 respectively. The mean difference of ANOVA was computed and the F value was found 4.77*, which was statistically significant at 0.05 level of confidence. To observe the statistically significant between the groups the researcher

conducted Tukey’s LSD (List Significant Difference) and the values were presented in table no 4.

Table No. 4: Tukey’s LSD test on State Anxiety in mean score comparison between the groups

Variables	Residing in old age home	Home dwellers living with family	Home dwellers living alone	Mean difference	t-value
State Anxiety	44.56	46.37		1.81	1.99
	44.56		50.19	5.63	3.30*s
		46.37	50.19	3.82	2.08*s

*The table values required for significance at $t_{0.05}$ level with DF (53) was 2.01, DF (39) was 2.02 and DF (44) was 2.02 respectively

Table no-4, shows that the significant difference were found in state anxiety between the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living alone, home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone and their mean difference were 5.63, 3.82 respectively. While there was no significant differences were found in state anxiety between residing old age home and home dwellers living with family group. According the Spielberger (1970) Anxiety Norms, indicated that the residing in old age home group and home dwellers living with family group possess moderate anxiety level whereas home dwellers living alone group possess over anxiety level.

4.3. Psychological Variables (Trait Anxiety) among the three groups were presented below-

Table no- 5. Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Trait Anxiety among Aged Men residing in old age homes, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone.

Variables	Group	N	Mean± SD	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	‘F’ Ratio
Trait Anxiety	Residing in old age home	25	44.92±6.16	Between	202.81	2	101.41	3.83*s
	Home dwellers living with family	30	45.80±4.91	Within	1722.66	65	26.50	
	Home dwellers Living alone	16	48.63±4.94	Total	1925.47	67		

*The table values required for significance at $F_{0.05}$ level with DF (2, 65) was 3.13

Table no- 5, indicates the mean value of trait anxiety of the three groups-Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 44.92, 45.80 and 48.63 respectively with SD value were 6.16, 4.91 and 4.94 respectively. The mean difference of ANOVA was computed and the F value was found 3.83*, which was statistically significant at 0.05 level of confidence. To observe the statistically significant differences between the groups the researcher conducted Tukey’s LSD (List Significant Difference) and the values were presented in table no- 6.

Fig 3: Graphical representations of Mean Value of Trait Anxiety.

Table no-6; Tukey’s LSD test on Trait Anxiety in mean score comparison between the groups

Variables	Residing in old age home	Home dwellers living with family	Home dwellers living alone	Mean difference	t-value
Trait anxiety	44.92	45.8		0.88	0.59
	44.92		48.63	3.71	2.03*s
		45.8	48.63	2.83	1.86

*The table values required for significance at $t_{0.05}$ level with DF (53) was 2.01, DF (39) was 2.02 and DF (44) was 2.02 respectively.

Table no- 6, shows the significant differences in trait anxiety between the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living alone and their mean difference was 3.71. While there was no significant difference found in trait anxiety between the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living with family group, home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone. According the Spielberger (1970) Anxiety Norms, the three groups were possess moderate anxiety level.

4.4. Psychological Variables (Behavioral Approach) among the three groups were presented below-

Table No. 7. Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Behavioral Approach among Residing in oldage homes, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone.

Variables	Group	N	Mean± SD	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	‘F’ Ratio
Behavioral Approach	Residing in old age home	25	30.96±7.13	Between	221.04	2	110.52	1.98 ^{n.s.}
	Home dwellers living with family	30	20.03±7.55	Within	3698.77	65	56.90	
	Home dwellers living alone	16	26.25±8.00	Total	3919.81	67		

*The table values required for significance at $F_{0.05}$ level with DF (2, 65) was 3.13)

Table no- 7 indicates the mean value in respect of behavioral approach of the three groups- Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 30.96, 20.03 and 26.25 respectively with SD value were 7.13, 7.55 and 8.00 respectively. The mean difference of ANOVA was computed and the F value was found 1.98, which was statistically not significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The differences were observed among the mean values in three groups

which were not significant differences. According to the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Coping Strategy Norms, indicated that the group residing in old age home possess moderate level of behavioral approach. While the home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone possess low deficient level of behavioral approach.

Fig 4: Graphical representations of Mean Value of Behavioral Approach.

4.5. Psychological Variables (Cognitive Approach) among the three groups were presented below-

Table no- 8. Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Cognitive Approach among Residing in old age homes, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone.

Variables	Group	N	Mean±SD	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Ratio
Cognitive Approach	Residing in old age home	25	13.12±3.00	Between	138.88	2	69.44	6.43*s
	Home dwellers living with family	30	12.10±3.66	Within	701.75	65	10.80	
	Home dwellers Living alone	16	8.88±3.40	Total	840.63	67		

*The table values required for significance at $F_{0.05}$ level with DF (2, 65) was 3.13

Table no-8, shows that the mean value in respect of cognitive approach of the three groups- Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone were 13.12, 12.10 and 8.88 respectively with SD value were 3.00, 3.66 and 3.40 respectively. The mean difference of ANOVA was computed and the F value was found 6.43*, which was statistically significant at 0.05 level of confidence. To observe the statistically significant differences between the groups the researcher conducted Tukey's LSD (List Significant Difference) and the values were presented in table no- 9

Fig 5: Graphical representations of Mean Value of Cognitive Approach.

Table No. 9: Tukey’s LSD test on Cognitive Approach in mean score comparison between the groups

Variables	Residing in old age home	Home dwellers living with family	Home dwellers living alone	Mean difference	t-value
Cognitive Approach	13.12	12.10		1.02	1.12
	13.12		8.88	4.24	4.19*s
		12.10	8.88	3.22	2.91*s

*The table values required for significance at $t_{0.05}$ level with DF (53) was 2.01, DF (39) was 2.02 and DF (44) was 2.02 respectively

Table no-9, shows the significant differences in cognitive approach between the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living alone, home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone and their mean difference were 4.24 and 3.22 respectively. While there was no significant difference was found in cognitive approach between the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living with family. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Coping Strategy Norms, indicates that the group residing in old age home and home dwellers living with family possess moderate level of cognitive approach whereas Home dwellers living alone possess low deficient level of cognitive approach.

4.6. Psychological Variables (Behavioral Avoidance) among the three groups were presented below-

Table No. 10. Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Behavioral Avoidance among Residing in old age homes, Home dwellers living with family and Home dwellers living alone.

Variables	Group	Numbers	Mean± SD	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	‘F’ Ratio
Behavioral Avoidance	Residing in old age home	25	16.92±8.15	Between	88.35	2	44.18	0,97n.s.
	Home dwellers living with family	30	19.07±4.10	Within	2973.93	65	45.75	
	Home dwellers living alone	16	16.00±8.29	Total	3062.28	67		

*The table values required for significance at $F_{0.05}$ level with DF (2, 65) was 3.13

Table no-10, shows the mean value in respect of behavioral avoidance of the three groups- Residing in old age home, Home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone were 16.92, 19.07 and 16.00 respectively with SD value were 8.15, 4.10 and 8.29 respectively. The mean difference of ANOVA was computed and the F value was found 0.97, which was statistically not significant at 0.05 level of confidence. According to the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Coping Strategy Norms, indicates that all the three groups were possess low deficient level of behavioral avoidance.

Fig 6: Graphical representations of Mean Value of Behavioral Avoidance.

5. Discussion

The purpose of the study is to survey the psychological status of elderly aged men who are living with their family or living alone and aged men living in old age homes. Psychological variables (State and Trait Anxiety) and Stress (Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach and Behavioral Avoidance) were measured through the Spielberger Anxiety Expression Inventory Questionnaire and the Stress Inventory Questionnaire adopted by Srivastava, A.K. After the analysis of data it was observed that the aged men who were living alone are experiencing high state anxiety level (50.19 ± 5.80) than the other two groups. The state anxiety level was moderate in those men living in old age homes (44.56 ± 5.00) and those living with family (46.37 ± 6.01). The trait anxiety level was found to be moderate in all the three groups (44.92 , 45.80 and 48.63 respectively) which were considered as moderate according to Spielberger Anxiety Expression Inventory Questionnaire norms.

While the Behavioral approach was found in moderate level in those living in old age homes (30.96 ± 7.13) and it was found in low deficient level in other two groups (20.03 ± 7.55 and 26.25 ± 8.00 respectively).

In Cognitive approach there were significant differences between those living in old age home and home dwellers living alone ($t_{0.05}=2.02$) and between home dwellers living with family and home dwellers living alone ($t_{0.05}=2.02$). Cognitive approach was to be found moderate in men living in old age home (13.12 ± 3.00) and home dwellers living with family (12.10 ± 3.66) where it low in those living alone (8.88 ± 3.40). Behavioral avoidance of all the three groups was found in low deficient level (16.92 ± 8.15 , 19.07 ± 4.10 and 16.00 ± 8.29) respectively.

6. Conclusions

The study throws up the following findings:-

- The state anxiety was high in elderly aged men. The anxiety level is high in the older population as they struggles with many factors like chronic health conditions, decreased functional ability, financial issues after retirement, loneliness etc (National Council of Aging).
- Cognitive approach was found low in those who were living alone. Study shows that connecting with other people through social activities and community progress helps to maintain their wellbeing and may improve their cognitive function (Cacioppo, et al. 2015).
- Behavioral avoidance was found low in all three groups. Study has been shown that high hope is extensively associated with high positive effect and high meaning in life whereas high experiential avoidance was associated with high negative affect and low meaning of life (Ferguson et al., 2017). The aged men avoids new job opportunities, relationship, social situations, recreational activities and family get-together as a natural coping mechanism for pain, trauma and other mental health issues. This behavior also refers to individual who actively avoid difficult feelings (www.choosingtherapy.com)

7. Limitations:

The researchers studied only the psychological status of elderly aged men but the factors like daily habits, chronic illness, fitness level and financial conditions were not taken into consideration. Despite these limitations the study helped to understand the anxiety and stress level of senior citizens. It was also found that elderly aged men who are living alone are having high level of anxiety which can lead to depression and low desire of living.

8. Recommendations:

Nearly 4 percent of older adult worldwide suffers from anxiety disorder and many goes undiagnosed due to misconceptions

about mental illness. So, it is necessary to bring awareness on anxiety disorder and can be address and treated through counseling and medication or both. Such studies can be conducted with more number of subjects which can focus more on the problem of older population. The same study can also be conducted on older women in order to understand their stress level.

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